

Corporate Governance Edifices of Indian Hospitality Businesses

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Abstract: This paper examines the relationship between Corporate Governance and Performance of the organization in Indian hospitality sector considering the corporate governance index. Two hundred and thirty six (236) organizations are selected on the basis of random sampling method from the population of six hundred and thirty two (632) organizations operated and listed in National Stock Exchange in the hospitality sector and data are collected from annual corporate governance and financial reports. The study uses Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CEM) of corporate governance index. Result establishes a significant relationship between Corporate Governance edifice and financial performance. The Corporate Governance index, viz., Board Size (BS), Board Duality (BD), Women Director on Board (WD), Independent Director (ID), Non-Independent Director (NID), Executive Director (ED), Non-Executive Director (NED), Total Committee (Tc), No. of Independent Director in Total Committee (NoIDTc), Return on Capital Employed (RoCE), Leverage, i.e., Debt to equity ratio (Lev), Return on equity (ROE), Return on assets (ROA) and Net profit Margin (NPM) play significant role in organizational performance. This study opens window for future research relating to the extent of Corporate Governance performance due to these corporate governance index including financial performance. Researchers can also test the CRAFTED model (Consistency, Responsibility, Accountability, Fairness, Transparency and Effectiveness of organizations) using the LOGIC (Leaning, Oversight, Guidance, Information and establishing a Culture of trust for the organizations) Principal of Corporate Governance in an organization.

Keywords: Corporate Governance, Economic Growth, Hospitality Business

JEL Classification: G34, O4, L66

1. Introduction

Corporate Governance as a policy and attribute of an organization is to achieve its long term corporate goals and to enhance its stakeholder's values. The best practices of corporate governance include a firm commitment and adoption of ethical practices. The *Laissez-faire* trade nowadays provides an edge to the organizations to prove its customer loyalty and to maximize profit. Corporate Governance integrals provide threat and challenges in policy implementation to any organization (Santiso, 2001).

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Corporate Governance as a set of systems, principles and processes follows set of guidelines to direct or control the company fulfilling its goals and objectives (Shleifer and Vishny, 1997). Corporate Governance dates back to Kautilya's *Arthashastra*, Machiavelli's *the prince* (1505) and Pluto's *the republic* as an integral part of the policy of the organization to work and add values. Corporate Governance as a framework (Fama and Jensen, 1983) ensures accountability, fair practices and transparency through its Board of Directors (Afsharipour, 2010) to its stakeholders including financiers, customers, management, employees, government and the community (Love *et al.*, 2002) at large. Corporate Governance's values, business conduct and procedures and processes customize the direction and control (Cadbury, 2000) and the mechanism of functions between the shareholders, directors, employees, auditors and the management.

The operational control collapse of mega corps in mid-1980 saw the seeds of corporate governance reforms initiated by Cadbury Committee in United Kingdom looking into 1991 London Stock Exchange faulty system of the governance of the corporates. Later Committees on reforms for corporate governance across globe was initiated which resulted into Sarbanes-Oxley Act, 2002, Cromme Code 2006, Kings III Code 2009, Companies Act, 2013 etc.

In India, the reforms were undertaken by CII Code, Kumar Mangalam Birla Committee, Naresh Chandra Committee, Narayana Murthy Committee, CII Task force on Corporate Governance 2009, Corporate Governance Voluntary Guidelines 2009 and Companies Act, 2013 which ultimately changed the working style of the Corporates. The wakeup call in India in Corporate Governance was given by the post economic liberalization period which concentrated on LPG (Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization). The attempt to de-regularization of industries and business saw the financial scandals of Satyam and Kingfisher acted as a final nail in the coffin to introduce some major reforms in the Corporate Governance. SEBI Clause 49 of listing agreement did allow companies to practice good Corporate Governance which came into existence after being introduced by Indian Stock Exchange on 31st December, 2005 which also contains statutory and non-mandatory requirements and provisions of the Companies Act, 1956. India, being a land of hospitality conferred its guests as God (AtihiDevoBhav). Hospitality travelled through Six Approach Theory (Lashley, 2000) to Three Domain Theory (Lashley and Morrison, 2000) and to Hospitality Context Model (Statlery, 2002) as a failed attempt to satisfy academicians and researchers. Academicians viewed Hospitality by the disciplines of culture and practice (Lashley *et al.*, 2007), are still to entrench (Hemmington, 2007). Hospitality being the world oldest, largest and most important industry (Pizam and Shani, 2009) still buttresses other industries for its growth.

2. Literature Review

The limited study confining literature is hospitality makes it vulnerable regard to other sectors of similar nature. The performance of hospitality industry by Bombay Stock Exchange (Gordon and Gupta, 2003) for its annual performance and corporate governance practices would establish its role as an organization with economic development and a legal framework (Jauhari, 2009) in unorganized sector and franchising industry (Dahlstrom et al., 2009). The aftermath of Satyam and Kingfisher frauds in India, initiatives to improve the corporate governance by establishing more stout measures to strengthen the existing corporate laws in order to regain the public trust, economic stability and investors' confidence in the system (Brockett and Rezaee, 2012) were initiated across the globe. The corporation's assurance for finance supply (Shleifer and Vishny, 1997) for maximum return on their investment controlled the residual claims (Epps and Cereola, 2008). The board size and capital structure (Berger *et al.*, 1997) established a negative leverage due to the presence of external directors (Yermack, 2004) but positive in debt in capital structure (Lipton and Lorsch, 1992) and financial position. Board and financial position plays a significant role in determination of control in relation to the practices established by an organization and seen as a mechanism to controls the organization (Kim *et al.*, 2005; Hassan *et al.*, 2008). The major sides of the corporate governance i.e. conformance and performance are seen as monitoring, supervising and being accountable to different stakeholders (Hassan and Halbouni, 2013) by contribution of managers for performance. Corporate Governance as a tool of administration, implementation of corporate governance codes and principles may or may result into reforms, but literature establishes causality between corporate governance and firm performance taking into account single governance variable (Yermack, 1996; Bhagat and Black, 2002). But due to the nature of the complex phenomenon of corporate governance some authors suggests that a corporate governance index should be taken into account while studding the impact of the corporate governance on firm performance (Gompers *et al.*, 2003; Core *et al.*, 2006; Brown and Caylor, 2006). The other argument of some of the researchers that good corporate governance results into better corporate performance leading to better financial results advocated reform in the field of corporate governance. Although there are some studies that suggest that there is no significant relationship between the corporate governance and firm performance (Buallay *et al.*, 2017). Although the relationship between corporate governance and firm performance has been studied and established in most of the developed countries (Hermalin and Weisbach, 1991; Kang and Shivdasani, 1995; Gompers *et al.*, 2003; Judge *et al.*, 2003; Barnhart *et al.*, 1994; Bauer *et al.*, 2004; Christopher and Lee, 2004; Bhagat and Bolton, 2008; Guest, 2008), it is still in the infancy stage in developing country like India and need to be studied accounting to either the corporate governance principles and codes and firm performance or the

corporate governance index and the firm performance. Most of the studies have been made in manufacturing, automobile and banking industry lacking behind the hospitality industry (Price *et al.*, 2015; Jauhari and Gunjan, 2012; Jauhari, 2009). Some researchers tried to establish the challenges, strategic and financial issues in hospitality with growth prospects. The small sample size restricts the hospitality study in India (Dwivedi and Jain, 2005; Ghosh, 2006; Garg, 2007; Jackling and Johl, 2009). Manufacturing organizations valuation on corporate governance index (Ghosh, 2006, Garg, 2007, Kohli and Saha, 2008) could establish the role of corporate governance.

This study aims to establish the relationship between Corporate Governance index and its effectiveness in delivery mechanism with the help of confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and propose suggestions for corrections in the mechanism.

3. Methodology

This present paper examines the Corporate and financial governance reports of two hundred and thirty six (236) Hospitality Companies obtained from primary and secondary source on the basis of random sampling method from CMIE (Center for Monitoring Indian Economy) Data base for the year 2006-2015 from the population of Six hundred and thirty two (632) organizations operated and listed in National Stock Exchange in the Hospitality Sector in India. Their Corporate annual performance report and Financial Reports analysis based on the facts and Exhibitors provided by these companies over the last ten years in their annual report as on 31st March, 2015, results are derived. The study variables included to analyze the corporate governance structure of hospitality industry were divided into Corporate Governance Variables and Financial Governance Variables. The Corporate Governance Variables included Board Size (BS), Board Duality (BD), Women Director (WD), Independent Director (ID), Non-Independent Director (NID), Executive Director (ED), Non-Executive Director (NED), Total Committee (Tc), No. of Independent Directors in total Committee (NoIDTc), Corporate Social Responsibility Expenditure (CSR), Firm Age (FA) and Year of Incorporation (YoI). The Financial Governance Variables Included Total Assets (TA), Sales (S), Reserves and Funds (R&S), Profit after Tax (PaT), Cash profit (CP), Net profit Margin (NPM), Paid up Capital Equity (PuEC), Return on Assets (RoA), Return on Equity (RoE), Leverage (Debt/Equity) (Lev), Return on Capital Employed (RoCE), Tobin Q (Tq) and Market Capitalization (MktCap). The Corporate Governance and Financial Governance Variables were first confirmed on the basis of Second order construct validity using Confirmatory Factor Analysis and then regression was used to study the impact of these corporate and financial variables on corporate governance.

The measurement model shown in the Exhibit 1 comprises of seventeen factors out of which ten are corporate governance variables and seven are financial performance of the

organization variables. . Each of these observed variables is regressed into its respective factor. Finally all the seventeen factors are shown to be inter-correlated. The factors which are confirmed after the CFA obtained from the SPSS AMOS 20 were BS, BD, WD, ID, NID, ED, NED, Tc and NoIDTc from the corporate governance variables and RoCE, Lev, ROE, ROA and NPM were from the financial variables with a significant loading factor. FA, PAT and TA vales were not significant in the CFA and hence they were excluded from the list of variables after CFA to be included from the list of variables for analyzing the effectiveness of corporate governance in hospitality industry. Table 1 shows the results of fit statistics of the Measurement model.

Exhibit 1: Contributory Factors of Corporate Governance

Table 1: Fit statistics of the Measurement model

Fit statistics	Recommended	Obtained	Fit statistics	Recommended	Obtained
X ²	-	2926.296	NFI	>0.90	0.91
df	-	988	RFI	>0.90	0.93
X ² significance	P <= 0.05	0.000	CFI	>0.90	0.92
X ² /df	< 5.0	2.96	TLI	>0.90	0.91
GFI	>0.90	0.91	RMSEA	>0.05	0.08
AGFI	>0.90	0.92	RMR	<0.02	0.004

3.1. Panel Data Analysis

Relationship between Corporate Governance Variables and Corporate Governance is expressed for panel data analysis as follows.

$$CG = \alpha + \beta1BS + \beta2BD + \beta3WD + \beta4ID + \beta5NID + \beta6ED + \beta7NED + \beta8Tc + \beta9NoIDTc + \beta10RoCE + \beta11Lev + \beta12ROE + \beta13ROA + \beta14NPM + \beta15ni(Dn) + \mu t$$

Where Dn = dummy variable for the year and n = no. of years.

4. Result Analysis - Corporate Governance Variables

The results showed in Table 2 establishes that ID, NID, ED, NED, NPM, ROA, ROE and Lev values were significant with the R² value as 0.5167 and the P value 0.00 (p < 0.01) with a Chi Square value 761.15 which signifies that the model is significant. The variable Independent Director (ID), Non-Independent Director (NID), Executive Director (ED), Non-Executive Director (NED), Net Profit Margin (NPM), Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE) and Leverage (Debt Equity Ratio) contribute significantly to the corporate governance of a firm. The results also establish that as the corporate governance increases, the financial performance of an organization also increases. The Board Size (BS), Women Director (WD) and No. of Independent Director in Total Committee (NoIDTc) have a negative coefficient value having a negative impact on the corporate governance while all other variables have a positive impact on the corporate governance. And corporate governance impacted the financial performance of the hospitality organizations significantly as the corporate governance had a significant positive relationship with financial performance obtained from the CFA model.

The analysis of the data obtained from primary and secondary sources from the year ranging 2006-2015 establishes the role of corporate governance of the hospitality industry for better financial performance. The Board Size (BS), Board Duality (BD), Women Director on Board (WD), Independent Director (ID), Non-Independent Director (NID), Executive Director (ED), Non-Executive Director (NED), Total Committee (Tc), No. of Independent Director in Total Committee (NoIDTc), Return on Capital Employed (RoCE), Leverage i.e., Debt to equity ratio (Lev), Return on equity (ROE), Return on assets (ROA) and Net profit Margin (NPM) were the factor which contributed significantly to the corporate governance of the hospitality industry established by the CFA of the variables taken for the study conducted with IBM SPSS AMOS 24. The study also establishes that Board Size (BS), Women Director (WD) and No. of Independent Director in Total Committee (NoIDTc) has negative impact on corporate governance of the firms under study while Independent Director (ID), Non-Independent Director (NID), Executive Director (ED), Non-Executive Director (NED), Return on Capital Employed

(RoCE), Leverage (Lev), Return on equity (ROE), Return on assets (ROA) has a positive impact enhancing the productivity and effectiveness of the organizations. The regression results between the corporate governance and the independent variables indicates that year taken as the dummy variable has a significant impact on the corporate governance which minimized the fixed specific effect of the years. The results indicated that ID, NID, ED, NED, RoCE, Lev, ROE and ROA values were significant ($p < 0.01$) and had impacted significantly on the corporate governance of the firms under study.

Table 2: Result of Random-effects GLS regression

Variable	Coefficient	t-statistics	Variable	Coefficient	t-statistics
BS	-.0201247	-1.06	Lev	.0123328	3.21
WD	.0072485	0.12	RoCE	.0053488	0.99
BD	-.0459669	-0.39	2007	-.0574748	-0.47
ID	.1189359	1.98	2008	-.0870801	-0.72
NID	.0345706	2.26	2009	-.1187024	-1.00
ED	.1004907	2.18	2010	-.1675194	-1.41
NED	.0470095	2.16	2011	-.1585614	-1.32
Tc	.0144033	0.29	2012	-.3586299	-2.91
NoIDTc	-.0829685	-1.34	2013	-.2349814	-1.88
NPM	.0003819	9.58	2014	-.4148278	-3.07
ROA	.0964308	10.27	2015	-.8006582	-5.33
ROE	.0044036	7.86	Constant	2.327388	17.32

Note: Number of observation = 845; Number of groups = 113; $R^2 = 0.5167$; $\chi^2 = 761.15$ and Prob = 0.0000 [95% Conf. Interval].

5. Conclusions

This study examines the relationship between corporate governance and performance of the organization in Indian hospitality sector. We test the corporate governance determinants to establish a relationship between practices of corporate governance edifices and financial performance and effectiveness of Boards which were responsible for transparency, consistency, accountability, responsibility and fairness. Survey techniques used for data collection reveals a significant relationship between corporate governance edifice and financial performance of an organization. Corporate governance would increase more transparency, consistency, accountability, responsibility, fairness and effectiveness of the Boards responsible for the results of the organizations. The best practices in corporate governance would develop a culture of continuous learning with an effective oversight of the management workings and guiding the organization for value creating strategies. The trust among the shareholders and the management can be built

through a culture of disseminating the correct and right information about the workings of the organization and providing the right information about the books of accounts.

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References

- Afsharipour, A., 2010, A Brief Overview of Corporate Governance Reforms in India, The Conference Board, 19.
- Ann, B. M. and Rezaee, Z., 2012, Corporate Sustainability Integrating Performance and Reporting, Does GRI Reporting Impact Environmental Sustainability, 571-580.
- Barnhart, S.W., Marr, M.W. and Rosenstein, S., 1994, Firm performance and board composition: Some new evidence, Managerial and decision economics, 15, 4, 329-340.
- Bauer, R., Guenster, N. and Otten, R., 2004, Empirical evidence on corporate governance in Europe: The effect on stock returns, firm value and performance, Journal of Asset management, 5, 2, 91-104.
- Berger, A.N. and Humphrey, D.B., 1997, Efficiency of financial institutions: International survey and directions for future research, European journal of operational research, 98, 2, 175-212.
- Bhagat, S., and B. S. Black, 2002, The Non-Correlation between Board Independence and Long-Term Firm Performance, Journal of Corporation Law, 27, 231-273.
- Bhagat, S. and Bolton, B., 2008, Corporate governance and firm performance, Journal of corporate finance, 14, 3, 257-273.
- Brown, L.D. and Caylor, M.L., 2006, Corporate governance and firm valuation, Journal of accounting and public policy, 25, 4, 409-434.
- Buallay, A., Hamdan, A. and Zureigat, Q., 2017, Corporate governance and firm performance: evidence from Saudi Arabia, Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal, 11, 1, 78-98.
- Cadbury, S.A., 2000, The corporate governance agenda, Corporate Governance: An International Review, 8, 1, 7-15.

Christopher, M. and Lee, H., 2004, Mitigating supply chain risk through improved confidence, *International journal of physical distribution & logistics management*, 34, 5, 388-396.

Core, J.E., Guay, W.R. and Rusticus, T.O., 2006, Does weak governance cause weak stock returns? An examination of firm operating performance and investors' expectations, *The Journal of Finance*, 61, 2, 655-687.

Dahlstrom, R., Haugland, S.A., Nygaard, A. and Rokkan, A.I., 2009, Governance structures in the hotel industry, *Journal of Business Research*, 62, 8, 841-847.

Durnev, A. and Kim, E.H., 2005, To steal or not to steal: Firm attributes, legal environment, and valuation, *The Journal of Finance*, 60, 3, 1461-1493.

Dwivedi, N., and Jain, A. K., 2005, Corporate governance and performance of Indian firms: The effect of board size and ownership, *Employee Responsibilities and Rights Journal*, 17, 3, 161-172.

Epps, R.W. and Cereola, S.J., 2008, Do institutional shareholder services (ISS) corporate governance ratings reflect a company's operating performance? *Critical Perspectives on Accounting*, 19, 8, 1135-1148.

Fama, E. F. and Jensen, M. C., 1983, Separation of ownership and control, *The journal of law and Economics*, 26(2), 301-325.

Garg, A.K., 2007, Influence of board size and independence on firm performance: A study of Indian companies, *Vikalpa*, 32, 3, 39-60.

Ghosh, S., 2006, Do board characteristics affect corporate performance? Firm-level evidence for India, *Applied Economics Letters*, 13, 7, 435-443.

Gompers, P., Ishii, J. and Metrick, A., 2003, Corporate governance and equity prices, *The quarterly journal of economics*, 118, 1, 107-156.

Gordon, J. P. and Gupta, P., 2003, Portfolio flows into India: do domestic fundamentals matter? Working Paper, International Monetary Fund.

Guest, P. M., 2008 The determinants of board size and composition: Evidence from the UK, *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 14(1), 51-72.

Hassan, C.H., Rahman, M.R.A. and Mahenthiran, R., 2008, Corporate governance, transparency and performance of Malaysian companies, *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 23, 8, 744-778.

Hemmington, N., 2007, From service to experience: Understanding and defining the hospitality business, *The Service Industries Journal*, 27, 6, 747-755.

Hermalin, B.E. and Weisbach, M.S., 1991, The effects of board composition and direct incentives on firm performance, *Financial management*, 29, 101-112.

Jackling, B. and Johl, S., 2009, Board structure and firm performance: Evidence from India's top companies, *Corporate Governance: An International Review* 17, 4, 492-509.

Jauhari, V., 2009, Hospitality, tourism and economic growth in India, *Worldwide Hospitality and Tourism Themes*, 1, 1, 7-11.

Judge, W.Q., Naoumova, I. and Koutzevol, N. 2003, Corporate governance and firm performance in Russia: an empirical study, *Journal of world business*, 38, 4, 385-396.

Hassan, K.M. and Halbouni, S.S., 2013, Corporate governance, economic turbulence and financial performance of UAE listed firms, *Studies in Economics and Finance*, 30, 2, 118-138.

Kang, J.-K., and Shivdasani, A., 1995, Firm performance, corporate governance, and top executive turnover in Japan, *Journal of financial economics*, 38, 1, 29-58.

Kohli, N. and Saha, G.C., 2008, Corporate governance and valuations: Evidence from selected Indian companies, *International Journal of Disclosure and Governance* 5, 3, 236-251.

Lashley, C., Lynch, P. and Morrison, A.J., 2007, *Hospitality: A social lens*, (Edited), Elsevier.

Lashley, C., Lynch, P. and Morrison, A.J., 2000, *Franchising hospitality services*, (Edited), Routledge.

Lashley, C., 2000, In search of hospitality: Towards a theoretical framework, *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 19, 1, 3-15.

Lipton, M., and Lorsch, J.W., 1992, A modest proposal for improved corporate governance, *The business lawyer*, 48, 1, 59-77.

Love, I. and Klapper, L.F., 2002, Corporate governance, investor protection, and performance in emerging markets, *The World Bank*.

Pizam, A. and Shani, A., 2009, The nature of the hospitality industry: present and future managers' perspectives, *Anatolia*, 20, 1, 134-150.

Price, L.L., Vaidyanathan, R., Rishi, M., Jauhari, V. and Joshi, G., 2015, Marketing sustainability in the luxury lodging industry: A thematic analysis of preferences amongst the Indian transition generation, *Journal of Consumer marketing*, 32, 5, 376-391.

Sanjeev, G.M. and Jauhari, V., 2012, The emerging strategic and financial issues in the Indian hospitality industry: an overview, *Worldwide Hospitality and Tourism Themes*, 4, 5, 403-409.

Santiso, C., 2001, Good governance and aid effectiveness: The World Bank and conditionality, *The Georgetown public policy review*, 7, 1, 1-22.

Shleifer, A. and Vishny, R.W., 1997, A survey of corporate governance, *The journal of finance*, 52, 2, 737-783.

Slattery, P., 2002, Finding the hospitality industry, *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport and Tourism Education*, 1, 1, 19-28.

Watson, S., 2008, Conceptual model for analysing management development in the hospitality industry: A UK perspective, *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 27(3), 414-425.

Yermack, D., 1996, Higher market valuation of companies with a small board of directors, *Journal of financial economics*, 40, 2, 185-211.

Yermack, D., 2004, Remuneration, retention, and reputation incentives for outside directors, *The Journal of Finance*, 59, 5, 2281-2308.